

Prevalence of Group a Human Rotavirus in Faeces of Calves in Sokoto State, Nigeria

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A study was undertaken to determine the prevalence of group A human rotavirus in cattle in Sokoto state, Nigeria. Information on the epidemiology of the virus in any area is necessary for vaccine development against the disease caused by the pathogenic agent. Immunochromatographic technique (Lateral Flow Rapid Test Strip from RIDA@QUICK) was used. Altogether 200 faecal samples were assayed from both diarrheic and non-diarrheic cattle. The total prevalence was 4 (2%). Prevalence of rotavirus infection according to breeds were: Sokoto Gudali (2.82%), White Fulani (1.28%) and Red Bororo (2.78%). According to the sex, male cattle recorded 3 (5.88%) prevalence and female cattle had 1 (0.67%) prevalence. Based on the season, the prevalence rate was found to be higher 4.16% during the hot season. The age prevalence was found to be higher in males (3.45%). There was significant association ($P<0.05$) between rotavirus infection with sex and season. No significant association was observed ($P>0.05$) between rotavirus infection with age and breed. To our knowledge this is the first-time study of this nature was carried out on rotavirus infection in cattle in Sokoto state and these findings shows a close relationship between herdsmen and their animals by sharing common source of drinking water in the livestock producing communities in Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Keywords: Cattle, Group A, Prevalence, Rotavirus, Sokoto State

INTRODUCTION

Gastroenteritis caused by rotavirus continues to be a major cause of death of neonates and infants in humans and animals in developing countries and a significant cause of high morbidity in the industrialized nations of the world (Kapikian and Chanock, 1996). Rotaviruses are the most common causes of acute gastroenteritis in the young of a number of mammalian and avian species

worldwide (Kapikian *et al.*, 2001). In 2004, six countries including Nigeria accounted for more than half of all rotavirus diarrheal deaths in children under five years of age (Ahmed *et al.*, 2009). Rotavirus disease is more severe than diarrhea caused by other enteric pathogens (Albano *et al.*, 2007). The cost of rotavirus diarrhea is high in developing countries where 20% to 70% hospitalizations and 800,000 of the three million deaths per year from diarrhea are caused by this pathogen (Glass *et al.*, 1997).

Hospital and community-based studies in Nigeria have

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shown that up to 33% of childhood diarrheas are associated with rotavirus infection (Omotade *et al.*, 1995; Adah *et al.*, 1997b). However, there are no documented studies on rotavirus in animals in Sokoto. Rotavirus infection can either be symptomatic or asymptomatic. The asymptomatic animals only shed the virus in the faeces with no clinical signs, they are therefore dangerous.

Proximity between humans and animals in many developing countries in Africa as well as sharing of common source of drinking water in the predominantly livestock producing communities in Sokoto will likely facilitate interspecies transmission of rotavirus as reported by Stacy *et al.* (2010). The spread of rotavirus is mainly through feco-oral transmission (CDC, 1998). Sokoto state ranks second highest in livestock production in Nigeria, interaction through the traditional animal husbandry practices predisposes humans to rotavirus infection. The epidemiological data on rotavirus infections in Africa are not yet sufficient (Cunliffe *et al.*, 1999; Armah *et al.*, 2001). There is dearth of information as it relates to studies of rotavirus in animals, especially in sub-Saharan Africa such as Nigeria. This study was aimed at determining the prevalence of rotavirus infection in cattle in Sokoto state, as a baseline data for future research in this part of the country.

Virology of the Virus

Rotavirus is a non-enveloped virus of the family Reoviridae with an icosahedral capsid 70nm across. It derives its name from the wheel like appearance it has when viewed under an electron microscope (Anderson and Weber, 2004). Its genome is made up of 11 segments of double stranded RNA held in the inner core of the three-layered virus (Anderson and Weber, 2004). The genome codes for 6 structural proteins (VP 1,2,3,4,6,7) and 6 non-structural proteins (NSP1-6) (Graff *et al.*, 2002). Once in the small intestine, the virus undergoes a change and becomes infective to the villi. Proteins then mediate the invasion of the host cells and replication of the virus genome (Anderson and Weber, 2004).

According to Vende (2002), rotavirus has six structural proteins namely VP1-VP4 and VP6, VP7. VP1 is part of the inner core of the virus and one of three proteins comprising the innermost of three viral layers (Vende *et al.*, 2002). It is the RNA-Dependent, RNA Polymerase for rotavirus (Varani *et al.*, 2002), a core replication intermediate (Vende *et al.*, 2002) and associates with VP2 at its icosahedral vertices (Vende *et al.*, 2002). VP2 protein is the main structural component of the innermost layer. It associates with VP1 and VP3 at its 12 vertices, and is a replication intermediate, VP3. The third part of

the inner core of the virus, acts as the mRNA capping enzyme. It also associates with VP2 and is a replication intermediate. Along with VP7, VP4 makes up the outer capsid of virus (Mendell *et al.*, 2000). It is an 88 kDa protein that dimerizes to create 60 spikes on virus surface (Golantsova *et al.*, 2004). According to Estes (2001), rotavirus has six non-structural proteins which are NSP1-NSP6. They include, NSP1 which binds Interferon Regulatory Factor (IRF) 3 and may inhibit interferon response during rotavirus infection (Graff, 2002). In conjunction with NSP5, NSP2 is involved in synthesis and packaging of viral RNA and creation of viroplasm. NSP2 is a replication intermediate (Vende *et al.*, 2002). NSP3, a 36kD protein, binds viral mRNA at the 3' end and promotes viral protein synthesis. It also represses host cell protein synthesis (Padilla-Noriega *et al.*, 2002). This protein is a possible target for a new class of antiviral (Varani *et al.*, 2002). NSP4 has been shown to act as an enterotoxin and cause diarrhea during infection (Mandell, 2000) There is also correlation between VP6 virus subgroup and NSP4 genotype (Itturiza-Gomara, 2003). This phosphoprotein works with NSP2 in RNA synthesis and packaging, and to induce viroplasm. It is also a replication intermediate (Vende *et al.*, 2002). Little information is available on NSP6, but it is associated with NSP5 and its function (Torres-Vega, 2000).

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Study Area

The study area is Sokoto, Sokoto state. The state is located at the extreme Northwestern Nigeria between longitudes 4° 8'E and 6° 54'E and between latitudes 12°N and 13°58'N. Sokoto forms boundaries with the Republic of Niger to the North, Kebbi state to the west and Southwest and Zamfara state to the East.

Sokoto state covers a total land area of about 32,000 square km. Based on the 2006 census, it has about 3,696,999 people suggestive of a population density of 97.7 persons per square km. The state has 23 Local Government Areas (LGAs). It is divided into 4 agricultural zones namely Gwadabawa, Isa, Tambuwal and Sokoto (Figure 1). Its sparse population has made available more large area of agricultural land and grazing areas for Sokoto than other states' economy, accounting for a significant proportion of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and responsible for about 70% of the total employment (NPC, 1991). Sokoto state ranks second in the nation's livestock population with 3 million cattle, 3 million sheep, 5 million goats, 4,600 camels and variable species of poultry including chickens, guinea fowls, ducks and turkeys (MOCIT, 2002).

Figure 1: Sokoto State map showing the Four Agricultural Zones of the State Source: Sokoto State Ministry of Agriculture and Natural Resources (2011)

Sample Collection

A total of 200 samples were collected from both calves and adult cattle and from both diarrheic and non-diarrheic cattle, over a period of six months. In this study, diarrheic cattle was defined as one passing loose, liquid, watery or bloody stool three or more times daily as reported by the owner. These samples were taken from eight (8) local governments in the state namely; Tureta and Sokoto North, Wurno and Sabon-Birni, Illela and Gwadabawa and Tambuwal and Yabo. Each two representing an agricultural zone in the four zones we have in the state. In these zones, each local government was divided into wards, institutional farms, Fulani herds and homes of individual who rear cattle for subsistence.

Ninety two (92) fecal samples were collected into sterile sample bottles during hot season (March-May) and one hundred and four (104) in the rainy season (June-August) from both diarrheic and non-diarrheic calves and cattle. Each sample was accompanied with a data sheet, indicating the breed, sample identification, age, sex description of the feaces (diarrheic and non-diarrheic).

Stool samples were collected in clean plastic sealed containers and the assays were done immediately after every sample was transported to the laboratory (within 24 hours). The screening was carried out at the Veterinary Public Health Laboratory of the Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, using RIDA@QUICK Rotavirus test strips, an *in vitro* diagnostic strip, for quick immunochromatographic (qualitative) determination of rotaviruses in stool samples. The test kit was supplied by r-biopharm intl. Darmsdt Germany.

Viral Detection

RIDA@QUICK Rotavirus test strips was used. It is an *in vitro* diagnostic strip, for quick immunochromatographic (qualitative) determination of group A rotavirus antigen in stool samples. The test kit was supplied by r-biopharm intl. Darmsdt Germany, and it was used according to the Manufacturer’s instruction. The test kit has 95% specificity and 100% sensitivity. The strips were read after 3-5 minutes, where a red and blue line is considered positive, and a blue line only is considered negative.

RESULTS

Table 1. The Overall Prevalence of Group A Rotavirus Infection in Cattle in Sokoto State

Group of animals tested	No. of Animals tested	Animals positive		Animals negative	
		No.	%	No.	%
Calves	87	3	3.45	84	96.55
Adults	113	1	0.88	112	99.12
Total	200	4	2	196	98

Table 2. The Age Prevalence of Rotavirus Infection in Cattle in Sokoto State

Age groups (months)	No. Examined	No. Positive	Prevalence(%)
0-8(calves)	87	3	3.45
9-36(Adults)	113	1	0.88
Total	200	4	2

$P > 0.05$ ($\chi^2 = 0.599$, $P = 0.438$)

Table 3. Prevalence of Group A Rotavirus Infection During the Two Seasons

No. screened	Season	Result		Relative Prevalence (%)
		Positive	Negative	
96	March-May(Hot Season)	4 (4.16%)	92 (95.83)	4.16
104	June- August (Wet Season)	0 (0%)	104 (100%)	0

$P < 0.05$ ($\chi^2 = 4.422$, $P = 0.036$)

Table 4. Rotavirus Infection in Relation to Sex of the Animals

Results	Sex	
	Male	Female
Positive	3 (5.88%)	1(0.67)
Negative	48 (94.12%)	148(99.33)
Total	51	149

$P < 0.05$ ($\chi^2 = 5.264$, $P = 0.0218$)

Table 5. Showing the Mean Relative Humidity of Sokoto State During the Study in 2011 (Source: Nigerian Meteorological Agency, Sokoto Sta)

Month (s)	Humidity (mmHg)
January	23
February	25
March	17
April	26
May	48
June	60
July	66
August	77
September	71
October	53
November	24
December	24

Table 6: Prevalence of Group A Rotavirus Infection in Cattle in Sokoto State based on Breed

Breed	No. screened	No. Positive	Prevalence (%)
White Fulani	78	1	1.28
Red Bororo	36	1	2.78
Sokoto Gudali	71	2	2.82
Other Breeds	15	0	0
TOTAL	200	4	2

P < 0.05 (t = 0.003, P < 0.05)

DISCUSSIONS

Two (2%) prevalence was recorded out of the 200 samples screened (Table 1). This is lower than the 3.2% recorded by Adah *et al.*, (2003), using ELISA and PCR in the north eastern Nigeria. The highest prevalence of 3.45% of rotavirus infection occurred in calves, this study was not entirely carried out in calves, 87 out of the 200 faecal samples screened in this study were from calves of between 0-8 months and 3(3.45%) were found to be positive (Table 2).

This further strengthen the findings by many authors that rotavirus is the chief culprit causing infection in young animals (Estes *et al.*, 1989; Kapikian, 2001; Susan, 2007). One of the most prominent epidemiological features of rotavirus gastroenteritis is commonly held to be its winter seasonality. This feature of the disease was recognised even before the virus was discovered and confirmed by early studies (Cook *et al.*, 1990). However, this study recorded 0% prevalence during the wet season (March-May), while a prevalence of 4.16% was recorded in the hot season (June-August).

Although the period was short, this study agrees with that of Morris *et al.* (1982) that describe low relative humidity rather than high relative humidity (Table 3) as the most important environmental factor for rotavirus survival and spread in Nigeria. The highest prevalence of 5.88% was recorded in male cattle and 0.67% in female (Table 4), In the table above table, the test for association of rotavirus infection with sex using Chi square test, shows a statistically significant association between sex and rotavirus infection, this agrees with the study carried out by Isidore *et al.*, (2010) in Burkina Faso, where more males were found to be positive (52.8%) than females.

Though there was no statistically significant association observed between rotavirus infection and breed, Sokoto Gudali, recorded the highest prevalence rate of 2.28%. Incidentally it is the most common breed of cattle amongst the breeds found in this locality. While the above risk factors (age, sex, and season) considered in this study has been compared with previous studies by other authors, breed specific prevalence found in this study could be accidental.

Conclusions and Recommendations

- It has been established that Group A rotavirus infection is prevalent in Sokoto state.
- There is dearth of information as it relates to the studies of rotavirus in animals especially in sub-Saharan Africa such as Nigeria, and therefore more researches are needed in this area.
- The study should serve as a challenge for further research, especially at molecular level
- In this study, 2% prevalence has been established for Group A rotavirus infection in cattle in Sokoto state.
- With its various sources of transmission, Rotavirus needs to be at the front burner of campaigns in ensuring food safety by stakeholders.
- Rapid emergence of new strains of rotaviruses, necessitates an intensive strain surveillance, especially in this part of the world.
- Efforts should be made towards developing and implementing a vaccine programme in animals.

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